

“MODULLI TENGLAMALAR VA TENGSIZLIKLAR” O‘QITISH METODIKASI

Boltaboyeva Muslima Egamovna

Farg‘ona viloyati Qo‘qon shahar 30- umumiy o‘rta ta‘lim maktabi,
“Matematika” fani o‘qituvchisi

E-mail: boltaboyevamuslima12@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7973555>

O‘zbekistonning iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy sohalarda yuqori natijalarga erishishi, jahon iqtisodiy tizimida to‘laqonli sheriklik o‘rnini egallay borishi, inson faoliyatining barcha jabhalarida zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalaridan yuqori darajada foydalanishning ko‘lamlari qanday bo‘lishiga hamda bu texnologiyalar ijtimoiy mehnat samaradorligining oshishida qanday ahamiyat kasb etishiga bog‘liq.

Ta‘lim jarayonini, oliy ta‘limning o‘quv reja va dasturlarini yangi pedagogik texnologiyalar va o‘qitish usullarini keng joriy etish, ta‘lim jarayonini sifat jihatdan yangilash va zamonaviy tashkiliy shakllarni joriy etish asosida yanada takomillashtirish;

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Sh.Mirziyoyevning 2017-yil7-fevraldagi “O‘zbekiston Respublikasini yanada rivojlantirish bo‘yicha Harakatlar strategiyasi to‘g‘risida”gi farmonida ta‘lim va ilm-fan sohasini rivojlantirish borasida belgilangan vazifalar ijrosini ta‘minlash hamda sohadagi dolzarb hujjatda ta‘lim muassasalarining moddiy texnik bazasini mustahkamlash yangi ta‘lim muassasalarini qurish, ta‘mirlash va kapital ta‘mirlash barobarida ularni zamonaviy o‘quv va laboratoriya jihozlari, kompyuter texnikasi va o‘quv metodik qo‘llanmalar bilan ta‘minlash nazarda tutilgan.

Xaqiqiy son a ning moduli deb, agar $a > 0$ bo‘lsa, bu sonning o‘ziga, agar $a < 0$ bo‘lsa, unga qarama qarshi son a ga aytiladi, a sonning moduli $|a|$ kabi belgilanadi.

O‘zgaruvchi qatnashgan tenglik tenglama deyiladi. O‘zgaruvchisi modul belgisi ichida qatnashgan tenglama modul qatnashgan tenglama deyiladi. Masalan: $|x|=1$, $|3x-5|=x$, $X^2-|x-1|=x$ tenglamalarning har biri modul qatnashgan tenglamadir.

Modul qatnashgan tenglamalarning amaliyotda eng ko‘p uchraydigan turlarini qaraymiz:

a) $|f(x)|=g(x)$ ko‘rinishidagi tenglama. Modulning ta‘rifiga ko‘ra o‘rinli bo‘lgan.

munosabatdan ko‘rinadiki, $|f(x)|=g(x)$ tenglamaning barcha yechimlarini topish uchun $f(x)=g(x)$ tenglamaning $f(x) \geq 0$ tengsizlikni qanoatlantiruvchi barcha yechimlarini va $-f(x)=g(x)$ tenglamaning $f(x) < 0$ tengsizlikni qanoatlantiruvchi barcha yechimlarini topish yetarli, ya‘ni $|f(x)|=g(x)$ tenglama.

$|3x-4|=1$ tenglamani yechamiz.

Bu tenglama, $|f(x)|=a$ ko‘rinishida va $a=1 \geq 0$. Shu sababli bu tenglamani yechish uchun $3x-4=1$, $3x-4=-1$ tenglamalarni yechish kifoya. Ularni yechib $x_1=1$, $x_2=$ larni hosil qilamiz.

b) $|f(x)|= f(x)$ ko‘rinishidagi tenglamani yechilishini ko‘rib chiqamiz. Bu tenglamani yechimi $f(x) \geq 0$ tengsizlikning yechimiga teng kuchlidir. Misol:

$|3x-6|=3x-6$ tenglamani yechamiz. Buning uchun quyidagi $3x-6 \geq 0$ tengsizlikni yechish kifoya. Demak, berilgan tenglamaning barcha yechimlar to‘plami $[2; +)$ oraliqdan iborat

c) $|f(x)|=|g(x)|$ bunday tenglamani yechish uchun, tenglamaning har ikkala tomonini kvadratga oshirib ishlash kifoya.

Masalan: $|2x-3|=|x+1|$ tenglamani yechamiz.

Tenglamaning har ikkala tomonini kvadratga ko‘tarsak, $(2x-3)^2=(x+1)^2$

yoki $4x^2-12x+9=x^2+2x+1$

Bundan, $X_1=4$ $x_2=$ yechimlarini topamiz.

d) Endi modul qatnashgan tenglamalarni yechishda eng samarali usullardan biri-"oraliqlar usuli" ni sizlarning e'tiboringizga havola etaman.

Masalan: $|x-1|-2|x-2|+3|x-3|=4$ tenglamani oraliqlar usulida yechamiz.

Bu tenglamani yechish uchun $x-1=0$, $x-2=0$, $x-3=0$ tenglamalarni yechib, $x=1$, $x=2$, $x=3$ sonlarni hosil qilamiz. Bu sonlar o'qini to'rtta (I,II,III,IV) oraliqqa ajratadi. Berilgan

tenglamani shu oraliqlarning har birida yechamiz.

Modul belgisi qatnashgan tengsizlik Modul qatnashgan tengsizlik deyiladi. Masalan: $|f(x)|\geq a$, $|f(x)|\leq|g(x)|$. Modulli tenglamalarni yechishning bir necha hil usullarini ko'rib chiqamiz.

Masalan: $|x-2|<1$ tengsizlik berilgan bo'lsin. Buni 2 xil usulda yechamiz.

1-usul. Tengsizlikning ikkala tomonini kvadratga ko'paytiramiz: $(x-2)^2 < 1$ yoki $X^2 - 4x + 3 < 0$. Hosil bo'lgan kvadrat tengsizlikning chap tomonini ko'paytuvchilarga ajratib, oraliqlar usulini tatbiq etsak, berilgan tengsizlikning barcha yechimlari to'plami (1;3) oraliqdan iborat ekanligini ko'ramiz.

3-usul. $|x|+1\leq 2|x-1|+3x$ bu tengsizlikni yechish uchun har bir modulni nolga aylantiruvchi sonlarni topamiz. $X=1$ va $x=0$. Bu nuqtalar son o'qini (- ; 0 , 0;1 , 1;+) oraliqlarga ajratadi. Ifodalarning bu intervaldagi ishoralari jadvalini tuzamiz:

Berilgan tengsizlik birinchi (- ;0 oraliqda $-x+1\leq 2(x-1)+3x$ ko'rinishiga keladi. Ixchmlashtirishlardan so'ng, $-2x\leq 1$ tengsizlik hosil bo'ladi, bundan $-0,5\leq x\leq 0$ kelib chiqadi.

Ikkinchi intervalda berilgan tengsizlik $x+1\leq 2(x-1)+3x$ ga yoki ayniy almashtirishlardan so'ng $0\leq x\leq 1$ ko'rinishiga keladi. Bu oraliqda ham tengsizlik yechimga ega

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